

A Study on Level of Stress Among The Top Executives in Public Sector Banks in Dindigul District

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Introduction

The paper is to study the stress among the executives of public sector banks in Dindigul District. For the purpose of this study, the executives who have been working in the public sector banks in Dindigul District have been selected. It does not include any other individuals and institutions which are directly or indirectly associated with banks.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are as follows

- To study the conceptual aspects of stress
- To study the level of stress among the top executives of the public sector banks in Dindigul District.
- To study the factors influencing the level of stress
- To give suitable suggestions for minimizing the stress among the executives of private and public sector banks.

Sample size

For this study 50 samples selected from public sector banks by using convenient sampling method. Thus, the sample respondents consisted of 50 executives of public sector banks in Dindigul District.

Methodology

The primary data were collected from the sample respondents through the questionnaire and by meeting top executives in their work place. This study is based on the primary data and secondary data. The secondary data were collected from offices of various branches of banks, regional offices of the banks, banking related web sites, newspapers, journals, and reports.

Data analysis

Age

Age	No of Respondents	%
Below 25	12	24
35-45	28	56
Above 45	10	20
Total	50	100

Gender

Gender	No. of Respondents	%
Female	18	36
Male	32	64
Total	50	100

Religion

Religion	No. of Respondents	%
Hindu	24	48
Muslim	4	8
Christian	22	44
Total	50	100

Marital Status

Marital Status	No. of Respondents	%
Married	38	76
Unmarried	12	24
Total	50	100

Annual Income

Annual Income	No. of Respondents	%
Below 1 lakh	15	30
1 – 2 lakhs	12	24
Above 3 lakhs	23	46
Total	50	100

Location

Location	No. of Respondents	%
Urban	5	10
Semi-urban	18	36
Rural	27	45
Total	50	100

Staff Strength

Staff strength	No. of Respondents	%
Below 10	13	26
10-20	23	46
Above 20	14	28
Total	50	100

From the above table the majority of the respondents are in the age group of 35-45, married. Also majority of the respondents have the earnings of Rs.3 lakhs and from rural areas. The majority of the strength of the bank is between 10-20 .

Level of Stress

S.No.	Age	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Below 25	5	3	3	11
2	35-45	8	4	4	16
3	Above 45	12	4	7	23
Total		25	11	14	50

S.No.	Religion	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Hindu	4	11	3	18
2	Muslim	4	9	3	16
3	Christian	5	9	2	16
Total		12	29	9	50

S.No.	Gender	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Female	8	17	3	28
2	Male	7	11	4	22
Total		15	22	7	50

S.No.	Annual Income	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Below 1 lakh	4	11	3	18
2	1 – 2 lakhs	3	9	8	20
3	Above 3 lakhs	4	5	3	12
Total		11	25	14	50

S.No.	Location	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Urban	2	8	3	13
2	Semi-urban	3	9	5	17
3	Rural	4	13	3	20
Total		9	31	8	50

S.No.	Staff Strength	Public Banks			Total
		High	Medium	Low	
1	Below 10	13	7	2	22
2	10-20	9	2	2	13
3	Above 20	7	4	4	15
Total		29	13	8	50

Findings

From the above table it is found that the majority of the respondents above the 45 years have experienced high level of stress. The respondents who belong to Hindu religion have experienced the high level of stress whereas the Christian and Muslim religions have experienced medium level of stress. The female respondents have experienced the high level of stress, the annual of the respondents from 1,00,000 to 2,00,000 have experienced the high level of stress, strength of the staff in the bank less than 10 and in the location from rural respondents experienced high level of stress.

Suggestions

People of all ages can go for walking, jogging, swimming, riding, bicycles, or playing tennis. so that they can get relieved of pre-occupied stresses that are stored in their minds. They can get relieved of stress , if they do these exercises. Time pressure is the prime source of stress for managers. The use of time management techniques would avoid stress. There is some research evidence that much meditation can have a desirable physical and mental impacts. Job should be enriched. They should have positive attitudes always. Stress management programmes should be conducted periodically.

Conclusion

It is unavoidable that every top executives incurs stress when he discharges his duties but he must know the art of overcoming stress. If he has less stress it will definitely uncrease his efficiency.

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